

Impact of the measurement conditions and compression paddle on mammography dosimeter response

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ABSTRACT

The effect of mammography measurement conditions was investigated to evaluate their impact on measurement uncertainties in clinical practice. The most prominent physical X-ray beam quantities i.e., – air kerma, half-value layer, and X-ray tube voltage – were examined by measuring the response of two ionization chambers and six X-ray multimeters (XMMs) of different models. Measurements were performed using several anode/filter combinations and both with and without the compression paddle in the X-ray beam. Maximum differences of higher than 6 % were found for all quantities when the dosimeter displayed value was compared with the reference value or the variation within the clinical anode/filter combinations Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh were considered. The study showed that the calibration procedure with the W/Al anode/filter combination was reliable only for ionization chambers, and the response of XMMs varies in such a way that the calibration coefficient cannot be predicted between various measurement conditions used in calibration and clinical practices. XMM calibrations are typically performed without a compression paddle in the beam, and the response of the XMM changes when radiation quality is slightly altered. If XMM specific data is not available, based on this study, an additional uncertainty of 2 % ($k = 1$) could be used as a typical estimate, at least for air kerma measurements. XMMs should be used for clinical measurements in mammography only with correct settings. If the correct settings are not available, the XMMs should not be used or used only with extreme caution.

1. Introduction

Mammography X-ray systems play a pivotal role in the detection of breast malignancies [1,2]. During the mammography examination, the breast is compressed by a compression paddle to achieve several benefits for optimized image quality, including reduced tissue thickness. This practice both enables lower radiation dose to patient and provides improved image contrast with minimized scatter and avoiding breast movement during image acquisition [3]. The radiation dose received by the patient during exams should be kept as low as reasonably achievable while maintaining acceptable clinical image quality [4,5]. Image quality is mainly optimized by adjusting exposure parameters that affect radiation quality, such as the anode and filter materials and thickness, and tube voltage (kV). Thereafter, the appropriate amount of radiation determined in terms of air kerma (K_a) is provided by adjusting the anode

tube current–time product (mAs). The generic term radiation dose is often used instead of air kerma in dosimeter displays and software.

The detector type used in mammography dosimetry is typically an ionization chamber or a semiconductor. Semiconductor-based detectors, which utilize the signal from multiple detection volumes with different filtrations, have recently become more common due to their robust structure, small size, and convenience of use [6]. These detectors typically offer a possibility to measure other exposure parameters in addition to air kerma, such as practical peak voltage (PPV), peak tube voltage (kVp) and half-value layer (HVL). The measurements are performed non-invasively, from exposure to the radiation beams. The term X-ray multimeter (XMM) is thus an appropriate name for such detectors. Many radiation dosimetry laboratories provide calibrations in terms of air kerma, but very few laboratories provide calibrations for the other quantities that can be measured by XMMs. However, to allow consistent

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and comparable results, measurements of all quantities should be traceable to the International System of Units (SI) through an appropriate chain of calibrations and uncertainty estimations.

Dosimeter calibration is an essential prerequisite in accurate estimation of patient dose. However, the calibration coefficient of a dosimeter is valid only under the conditions specified in the accompanying calibration certificate. Therefore, differences between the conditions applied during the calibration procedures and those used in clinical measurement conditions should be considered with respect to the overall uncertainty budget. For this reason, it is essential to be aware of how changes in the conditions will influence the response of the dosimeter. For mammography dosimetry, calibration laboratories traditionally use standardized reference radiation qualities defined by the anode/filter combination, tube voltage, and HVL in the IEC 61267 standard [10] or they have utilized an existing X-ray tube with W-anode and use it with a specific filtration (often 0.5 – 0.7 mm Al). The reference conditions defined in the standard are typically established using industrial-type (i.e. non-clinical) X-ray tubes and horizontal beams without additional attenuating and scattering objects such as a compression paddle in the beam. This differs significantly from the clinical measurement geometry and conditions.

Because dosimeters are used in clinical practice with a large selection of radiation qualities, the energy dependence of their response under variable conditions must be known. The recommended limit of variation for all dosimeters is less than $\pm 5\%$ [11]. For ionization chambers, the energy dependence of their air kerma calibration coefficient is typically moderate and well-defined, whereas semiconductors show a much stronger energy dependence [12]. Dosimeter manufacturers have developed solutions for internal correction for different radiation qualities, and the response of an XMM can be reasonably good [6–9,13]. However, especially in mammography, the range of radiation qualities available in clinical practice is extensive, because current mammography equipment offers many different anode and filter materials with K-edge at appropriate energy for optimized imaging, resulting in significant changes in the shape of spectra [14]. XMMs are sensitive to changes in spectra, and thus, it is important to select the applied anode/filter combination from the detectors' software to enable reliable results based on appropriate correction factors.

Because the performance of the dosimeter might change based on the selected parameters, the XMM should be calibrated with all selections that are clinically relevant. However, only a limited number of radiation qualities and conditions, typically based on international standards [10], can be established and maintained in calibration laboratories, and it is recognized that these do not fully cover the clinical range of radiation qualities. The nominal selection of the anode and filter will not solely define the radiation spectrum in use. Small changes, e.g., in the X-ray system filtration and compression paddle, can result in differences in the radiation spectra and thus in the XMM response. Furthermore, the reference mammography qualities do not consider the inclusion of a compression paddle in the beam. Therefore, even though nominally the same anode and filter combination would be used both in calibration and clinical measurements, the addition of a compression paddle in clinical measurements will introduce, in addition to attenuation and scatter effects, a difference in the radiation quality [15–17]. The position of the compression paddle also introduces alterations in the scattered radiation [18,19]. The American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM) recommends performing all the measurements with the CP positioned as close to the X-ray tube as possible [20]. There is not enough data in the literature on the impact of compression paddle use on XMM performance; therefore, the estimation of the related uncertainties is challenging for the clinical environment.

This study aims to evaluate the response of different dosimeters measured under various anode/filter conditions as well as the impact of the use of a compression paddle on the response. The influence on K_a , HVL, and PPV measurements is studied. These results can be used to estimate related uncertainties and help medical physicists and other

technical personnel in hospitals involved in patient radiation dose assessment in mammography.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Facility, X-ray system and radiation qualities

The experiments were performed at the Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratory of the Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK), Finland. The laboratory is a designated institute that maintains national measurement standards for ionizing radiation and provides calibrations for end users. The calibrations for mammography dosimeters were performed using an industrial X-ray system (GE, ISOVOLT TITAN 160 kV) with a tungsten anode and an anode angle of 20° . A transmission monitoring chamber PTW 786 and a collimation system are fixed parts of the setup. The reference radiation qualities for calibrations use an added 0.5 mm Al filtration with tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV.

In addition, the laboratory has a clinical mammography system, an Alpha RT mammography system (Instrumentarium Imaging). The system has a molybdenum target with an anode angle of 16° . It provides two optional filters: 30 μm of molybdenum (Mo) and 30 μm of rhodium (Rh) and operates with tube voltages between 20 kV and 35 kV. The Mo/Mo anode/filter combination, without the compression paddle and with tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV, complies with the requirements for RQR-M radiation qualities defined in the IEC 61267 standard [10]. All measurements were performed using a fixed tube current–time product of 100 mAs for all radiation qualities. The focus – image detector distance is 60 cm, and the cover surface of the image detector is 1 cm higher at a distance of 59 cm. The compression paddle (CP) 21 x 24 (Code 31515, 1999) of the mammography system has a thickness of 2 mm \pm 0.3 mm. The CP is removable, and the measurements were performed with (yCP) and without (nCP) the compression paddle in the beam.

2.2. Reference standards

2.2.1. Air kerma

A Radcal RC6M ionization chamber connected to a Keithley electrometer (model 6517B) is the Finnish national standard of air kerma and was used as the reference standard for air kerma measurements in industrial and clinical X-ray system setups. The standard has traceable calibration to the primary standards dosimetry laboratory at (Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, PTB, Germany,) for the reference radiation qualities generally used for calibration services, i.e., those based on W-anode and added 0.5 mm Al filtration. Moreover, the chamber has been calibrated by PTB for W-anode with 0.075 mm Ag-filtration (25–35 kV) and ISO 4037 low-energy radiation qualities (H and N series ≤ 40 kV) [21]. In addition, the same chamber has been calibrated in 2023 by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) for several mammography radiation qualities, including Mo/Mo (IEC 61,267 RQR-M [10]) and Mo/Rh anode/filter combinations with tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV. The HVL values at the IAEA and STUK were close enough so that no radiation quality corrections were required, and the calibration coefficients from the IAEA certificate were directly used for STUK beams. The chamber was also cross-calibrated against a PTW 23344 ionization chamber, which has a calibration traceable to the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM) for IEC 61267 RQR-M radiation qualities.

The spectra of the above-mentioned radiation qualities were appreciably different, and the HVL ranged from 0.27 mm Al to 0.7 mm Al. Still, the maximum deviation of the calibration coefficient is $< 0.7\%$, which is smaller than the measurement uncertainties of the calibration coefficients. Thus, the energy dependence of the reference chamber is very small, and it was estimated to introduce an additional uncertainty component of $< 0.2\%$ ($k = 1$) when the calibration coefficient is directly

used for nominally the same radiation quality with and without the compression paddle.

The REF chamber has a special construction where the chamber volume behind the thin entrance window is followed by a small plastic phantom body. The benefit of this construction is that even though the chamber is calibrated free in air, the phantom body produces back scatter to the chamber collecting volume. Therefore, when the chamber is positioned directly on a surface, the impact of scattering from the surface is reduced. Based on our measurements, the maximum impact of image detector was 0.7 % and this was considered in the uncertainty budget.

The reference values for air kerma were determined for radiation qualities (q) with and without the compression paddle in the radiation beam using Equation (1). For each radiation quality, charge measurements were performed with the reference chamber (REF), and corrected to the normal air temperature of 20 °C and pressure of 101.325 kPa (NTP) and multiplied by the calibration coefficient of the reference standard.

$$K_{a(\text{REF},q)} = M_{\text{REF},q} k_{T,P} N_{K(\text{REF},q)} \quad (1)$$

where,

$K_{a(\text{REF},q)}$ is the air kerma for the reference chamber,

$M_{\text{REF},q}$ is the measurement (charge) obtained with the reference chamber,

$k_{T,P}$ is the correction factor for the environmental conditions,

$N_{K(\text{REF},q)}$ is the calibration coefficient of the reference standard.

2.2.2. HVL values

The reference values for HVL were established using the recommendations given by TRS-457 [22] in industrial and clinical X-ray system setups. The measurements were performed in “narrow beam” geometry, and the collimator aperture produced a beam that covered the diameter of the chamber to irradiate it completely and uniformly. Different combinations of filters from a set of 0.05—0.1 mm thick aluminum with ≥ 99.9 % purity were used.

Measurements were made with the REF and corrected to NTP. No corrections for the difference in spectra were made due to the small energy dependence of the REF, and this impact was only considered in the uncertainty budget. The natural logarithm of the air kerma values were plotted as a function of the HVL-filter thickness, a linear equation was fitted to the results/values, and the HVL was solved at the point where air kerma value without HVL-filters is halved.

2.2.3. Practical peak voltage

X-ray tube voltage is a general term and different quantities are used for the quantification [23]. The PPV is the quantity recommended by IEC standard and is defined from timely variation of the X-ray tube voltage based on a specific weighting function [24]. The X-ray tube voltage of the industrial X-ray tube is calibrated against a calibrated high-voltage divider. The values are verified regularly by X-ray spectrometry measurements, and a monitor chamber is used in the beam to control the X-ray tube output so that any small tube voltage variations can be detected. The X-ray system has a constant potential and a small ripple; thus, the measured average tube voltage and PPV are essentially equal.

For the clinical X-ray tube, the reference kVp was determined using a commercial X-123 CdTe spectrometer (Amptek, Inc., USA). The spectrometer was calibrated in terms of photon energy using Am-241 and Eu-152 sources available at both the Italian Ionizing Radiation National Metrology Institute (ENEA-INMRI) and STUK. The determination of the kVp was obtained by estimating of the spectrum endpoint energy, defined as the highest energy of primary photons emitted by an X-ray tube, excluding the background measurement and pile-up counts.

Two methods were implemented to determine the endpoint. The first method was implemented using Python code to analyze the

experimental spectrum, which was first smoothed with adaptive-degree Savitzky-Golay smoothing [25]. This method decreases the statistical fluctuations of the energy bin counts. The code calculates the slope of the lines tangential to the end part of the spectrum and selects an energy range in which the slope is sufficiently stable. Thereafter, a linear fit on the smoothed spectrum is performed in this energy range. A frequent problem with this method is the choice of the ideal energy range in which to perform the linear regression. To ensure the goodness of the fit, the energy range was chosen to maximize the R^2 coefficient. The intersection of this optimized fit line with a linear fit to the background provides the value of the endpoint energy.

In the second method, an estimation of the mean background counts (C_b) was obtained from the measured background spectrum. Then an algorithm starting from the end of the measured spectrum searched the first channel with the number of counts (C) such that $C > 2.5 \cdot C_b$. This channel corresponds to the endpoint energy. The value $2.5 \cdot C_b$ was chosen because it was assumed that the background counts have a triangular distribution and that the minimum and maximum counts were known, making it possible to estimate the central value. The standard deviation was determined for $2.5 \cdot C_b$ value and the probability of occurrence was 5%, ensuring that the number of counts (C) was generated from primary photons.

Based on the estimates using the two methods described above, it is assumed that the real value of the endpoint energy is uniformly distributed within the range of the pair of estimated values; therefore, a rectangular distribution is considered with the endpoint energy values estimated as its extremes. The estimated endpoint energy is obtained as the mean value of this distribution. The combined uncertainties involved in this procedure are evaluated and included in the uncertainty budget.

The energy calibration was obtained only in the energy region of interest for this study, which essentially eliminates all problems due to incomplete charge collection typical of these instruments [26]. The kVp was measured for the molybdenum filter of the clinical mammography system. The spectrometer was placed at a vertical deflection angle of about 16 degrees, conforming to the anode angle, and to be congruent with the central beam axis. The spectrometer’s collimator (nominal hole diameter of 400 μm) was positioned directly on the detector’s surface without the brass cylinder which was introduced some characteristic peaks in the measured spectrum due to the zinc and copper contained in brass. In the estimation of the endpoint energy, the shape of the spectrum is not important; hence, during the measurements, additional copper filters (thickness of 0.1 mm) were added to the top of the detector, with thickness depending on the value of the tube voltage, to reduce the beam intensity and therefore to minimize electronic pile-up. This procedure, involving the use of a spectrometer, provides a measure of the spectrum endpoint energy for each voltage applied to the mammography X-ray tube using a non-invasive method.

In addition, in this case, it is expected that with our clinical X-ray systems the measured kVp is very close to PPV. This was confirmed by using the wave representation and comparing different tube voltage related parameters (kVp, PPV and average tube voltage) provided by some XMMs. The differences between these values were less than 0.1 kV, and therefore it was considered that the measured kVp can be used as a reference value for all the measurements regardless of what detectors were used interchangeably. The potential difference between the kVp and PPV quantities was evaluated and included in the uncertainty budget.

2.3. Dosimeters tested

The dosimeters used in this study are presented in Table 1. Two ionization chambers of the same type (IC1 and IC2) were used in the air kerma measurements. The structure of these chambers is similar to REF and the chamber body reduces the impact of back scattering when the chamber is positioned directly on a surface. The XMMs are protected

Table 1
Dosimeters used in this study.

Manufacturer	Detector model	Measuring Assembly	Reference Point ^a	Detector Code
Radcal	10x6-6 M	Accu Gold	17 mm from the bottom	IC1/IC2
RaySafe/Unfors	Xi	Xi (FW: 6.01)	7 mm from the top	XMM1
RaySafe/Unfors	X2	Touch screen interface	11 mm from the bottom	XMM2
Radcal	AGMS-DM+	Accu Gold	3.2 mm from the top	XMM3
RTI Group	MPD	Barracuda Palm Computer	8.13 mm from the top	XMM4
RTI Group	R100B	Barracuda Palm Computer	4.4 mm from the bottom	XMM5
RTI Group	Mako	Ocean Next	3.0 mm from the top	XMM6

^aDefinitions according to manufacturer's manual.

from back scattering. The manufacturers' specifications for dose (air kerma), HVL, and tube voltage (kVp, kVp average, PPV) for the XMMs are shown in Table 2. The different quantities were measured non-invasively from a single exposure except for few cases (Table 2, note 2). The XMMs require a selection of radiation quality (anode/filter) before the exposure to allow appropriate corrections for different quantities.

The detectors were calibrated following the laboratory's routine calibration procedure using the industrial X-ray tube with W/Al anode/filter combination. The anode/filter selection for the W/Al beam was available for XMM2, XMM4 and XMM6; thus, valid calibration could only be provided for these detectors. However, the other XMMs were tested in the W/Al beam by selecting an incorrect combination (Mo/Mo, nCP) to indicate potential errors and challenges related to current calibration practices.

In addition, the detectors were calibrated using the clinical mammography system. The detectors XMM1, XMM2, XMM3, XMM4, and XMM6 have separate selections for Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh anode filter combinations, and the appropriate combination was used according to the actual setting in the mammography equipment. However, in the older detector model XMM5, only Mo/Mo can be selected in the mammography mode.

In addition to the selection of radiation quality, four detectors (XMM1, XMM2, XMM4 and XMM5) have a separate option for the use of CP in the Mo/Mo beam. The manuals state that the detector considers the CP as having an equivalent aluminium thickness of an additional 0.1 mm. During the measurements, the selections were made according to the actual measurement setup (yCP and nCP). However, because the calibration service is typically performed without CP and clinical measurements apply CP, the potential impact of CP selection on response is

Table 2
Manufacturer's specifications (range and maximum error) for the dosimeters.

Detector	Dose		Half-value layer		Tube voltage		
	Range minimum ¹ (μGy)	Maximum error (%)	Range (mm Al)	Maximum error (%)	Range Mo/Mo (kV)	Range Mo/Rh (kV)	Maximum error (%)
IC1/IC2	0.1	5		N.A		N.A	
XMM1	5.0	5	0.2 – 1.2	5	20 – 40	25 – 40 ²	2
XMM2	1.0	5	0.2 – 3.6	5	18 – 40	32 – 40 ²	2
XMM3	0.04	5	0.21 – 0.50	5	21 – 49		2
XMM4	0.2	5		N.A	18 – 49	22 – 44	Mo: 1.5, Rh: 2
XMM5	0.0001	5		N.A		N.A	
XMM6	0.001	5	0.2 – 4.0	5	18 – 49		1.5

¹The range maximum is > 100 Gy for all detectors.

²To measure the kVp, 2 mm Al sheet had to be placed on the top of the detector in a separate exposure.

not covered in the calibration. Therefore, this was studied using an additional set of measurements by applying an incorrect selection of CP.

Based on the data in the manuals, most XMMs measure kVp or average kVp instead of PPV. Only XMM3 and XMM4 give separate values for PPV, which were used in this study. However, for the other XMMs, another tube voltage –related value given by the detector had to be used. The potential difference between these two quantities was considered in the uncertainty budget.

2.4. Measurement setup

The general procedures proposed in the International Dosimetry Code of Practice TRS-457 by the IAEA [22] were implemented in the calibrations. Measurements obtained using the reference ionization chamber were corrected to NTP. However, for IC1, temperature and pressure corrections were performed automatically, and for IC2, automatic temperature correction was performed, and XMMs do not require NTP corrections because they are based on solid-state detectors.

In measurements with the industrial X-ray system the dosimeter was positioned free in air in the central axis at a distance of 1 m from the X-ray focus using a laser-based alignment system. The calibrations were performed without a compression paddle in the radiation beam.

In clinical X-ray system measurements, the dosimeters were positioned on top of the mammography image detector surface, with the center of the sensitive volume placed 6 cm from the chest wall side. An additional PMMA plate with a thickness of 0.5 cm with positioning markings was used on the image detector surface for all dosimeters to allow accurate and repeatable positioning of different dosimeters. Therefore, the focus-to-detector reference point distance (FDD) of 56.8 cm (59 cm – 0.5 cm – 1.7 cm) was selected based on the REF chamber position. For the measurements performed using the XMMs, additional PMMA sheets were added between the mammography table and the dosimeters to enable the same FDD in each case. In the case of XMM2, the FDD was accidentally slightly different (57.3 cm), and additional REF measurements were performed to obtain the reference values for this specific case. Fig. 1 shows the setup used during the measurements with and without the compression paddle in the radiation beam. In the yCP measurements, the compression paddle was positioned as far away as possible from the dosimeter, at a distance of 44.5 cm from the focal spot.

2.5. Determination of the calibration coefficient

The calibration coefficient for air kerma was determined for all dosimeters shown in Table 1 and for XMMs using the quantities defined in Table 2. The calibration coefficient for these quantities and parameters (P) were obtained for different radiation qualities by calculating the ratio between the reference value (ref) and the values obtained for the dosimeters (d) to be calibrated, as shown in Equation (2).

Fig. 1. The setup used for the measurements: (A) with and (B) without the compression paddle.

$$N_{P,q} = \frac{P_{(\text{ref},q)}}{M_{d,q}} \quad (2)$$

where,

$N_{P,q}$ is the calibration coefficient of the dosimeter under calibration, at the radiation quality q ,

$P_{(\text{ref},q)}$ is the reference value obtained with the reference system,

$M_{d,q}$ is the reading of the measurement obtained with the dosimeter under calibration.

The deviation of $N_{(P,q)}$ from 1 indicates the difference from the reference value. The maximum deviation defines the maximum intrinsic error (MIE), and it can be compared with the value provided in the manufacturer's specifications (Table 2) for each parameter. The MIE indicates the maximum error that would be introduced if the dosimeter were used without any calibration coefficient.

To estimate the maximum variation related to the energy dependence of the response within specified radiation qualities, the difference between the lowest and highest calibration coefficients can be calculated. To compare the energy dependence with the requirements given in IEC standards, the calibration coefficient measured with different radiation qualities was compared with the value measured with the same anode/filter and reference tube voltage, k_{kV} . For air kerma and HVL, the reference tube voltage of 28 kV was used according to IEC 61674 [11], and for PPV, the reference voltage was 30 kV according to IEC 61676 [24]. Both standards give a limit of $\pm 5\%$ for the energy dependence of the response. In addition, calibration coefficients were used to calculate the maximum errors related to changes in calibration and measurement conditions.

2.6. Impact of the measurement conditions and compression paddle

Fig. 2 shows how the impact of the measurement conditions, including the usage of the compression paddle, was determined and compared for this study. The laboratory's routine calibration procedure, measurement condition (1) (MC1), was performed using an industrial X-ray tube, W/Al anode/filter combination, and nCP. The new calibration setup introduced the use of condition (2) (MC2) with a clinical X-ray tube, Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh radiation qualities, and nCP. Condition (3) (MC3) represents the clinical measurements with the clinical X-ray tube, Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh radiation qualities, and yCP. The aim of this study was to compare the typical calibration conditions MC1 and MC2 with

Fig. 2. Calibration coefficients were determined under three different measurement conditions (MC), and comparisons between the conditions were performed. The impact of the presence of a compression paddle (CP) with different anode/filter combinations was studied. The selections in dosimetry programmes are shown in square brackets, and the # symbol indicates an incorrect selection that is inconsistent with the MC. A more detailed description of the different conditions is given in the text.

clinical measurement condition MC3 to determine the impact of the current calibration condition (MC1=>MC3) and the usage of CP (MC2=>MC3) on the response of the dosimeter calculated using the defined calibration coefficients.

The selection of radiation quality and CP in the XMM software was always performed according to the actual use (1A and 2A, see Fig. 2), if available. However, in condition (1), the incorrect selection of radiation quality 1B was used because three dosimeters did not have the W/Al selections available (XMM1, XMM3, XMM5). In condition 2B, the incorrect selection of CP presence was intentionally used to determine the influence of that selection on the measurements with Mo/Mo anode/filter combination for XMM1, XMM2, XMM4, and XMM5, where this CP selection was available.

Because the radiation quality changes between the different conditions, the correct use of the calibration coefficient is not straightforward. For ionization chambers, HVL is typically used as a radiation quality specifier to interpolate the calibration coefficients expressed in terms of the quantity K_a when the chamber response changes as a function of radiation quality. However, the response of XMM might not follow any physical parameter because the response is adjusted based on a software solution; therefore, interpolations might not be possible. In this study, the calibration coefficient was directly compared between different conditions using anode/filter combination as a radiation quality specifier and by interpolating calibration coefficients from one condition to another using HVL.

The impact of the measurement conditions and compression paddle was determined for air kerma, HVL, and PPV for each radiation quality.

The impact was calculated by the maximum deviation of the calibration coefficients in percentage, obtained with condition MC1 or MC2 in relation to condition MC3, as given in Equation (3):

$$I_{CC,q} = \frac{(N_{P,q(MC1,MC2)} - N_{P,q(MC3)})}{N_{P,q(MC1,MC2)}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where,

$I_{CC,q}$ is the impact of the measurement conditions and compression paddle in percentage, at the radiation quality q ,

$N_{P,q(MC1,MC2)}$ is the calibration coefficient obtained under MC1 or MC2 without the compression paddle in the radiation beam,

$N_{P,q(MC3)}$ is the calibration coefficient obtained under clinical MC3 with the compression paddle in the radiation beam.

2.7. Uncertainty

A detailed analysis of the uncertainty components for the measurements was performed following international guidance [27]. Combined and expanded relative uncertainties (95 % confidence level, $k = 2$) were calculated for the calibration coefficients. In addition, the calibration coefficients for nCP and yCP were compared as a ratio. In this case, many uncertainty components were correlated and could be ignored, and the uncertainty to evaluate the significance of the difference was significantly smaller. All estimated uncertainties are briefly explained below and summarized in Table 4.

The most relevant uncertainty components for the calibration coefficient in terms of air kerma are shown in Table 3. The components are related to the measurements performed with both the reference chamber and tested dosimeters. The largest contribution to uncertainty originated from the calibration coefficient and the long-term stability of the reference chamber, as well as the stability of the air kerma rate of the X-ray system. The environmental conditions (air temperature and pressure) impact the air density inside the ionizing chamber, which is corrected for the chamber reading. However, the conditions (inc. humidity) also affect photon attenuation in air and depend on the measurement distance, which affects both ICs and XMMs.

As shown in Table 3, the uncertainty components were in general slightly larger in the clinical setup compared in the industrial setup. The industrial X-ray system was used in a calibration bunker with strictly

Table 3

Uncertainty budget for the determination of the calibration coefficient in terms of air kerma using industrial and clinical X-ray tubes under laboratory conditions.

Uncertainty components (%) ($k = 1$)	Industrial			Clinical	
	W/Al	Mo/Mo	Mo/Rh	Mo/Mo	Mo/Rh
Reference value					
Calibration coefficient	0.50	0.65	0.70		
Long term stability	0.58			0.58	
Difference in spectra	0.12			0.17	
Uniformity of the radiation field	0.06			0.12	
Measurement of charge	0.09			0.20	
Environmental conditions	0.03			0.16	
Scatter and others	0.06			0.70	
Measurement with tested dosimeters					
Position (setup)	0.23			0.31	
Uniformity of the radiation field	0.12			0.24	
Read-out of the meter	0.17			0.16	
Environmental conditions	0.03			0.05	
Change in photon attenuation in air	0.69			0.40	
Irradiation time	0.17			–	
Stability of air kerma rate	0.58			0.58	
Change in scatter conditions				0.58	
Others	0.12			0.12	
Combined standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)	1.25	1.54	1.56		
Combined expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	2.5		3.1		

controlled environmental conditions. A monitor chamber was applied to validate the X-ray beam output, and dosimeters were positioned free in air to minimize scattering. Measurements with the clinical X-ray tube were also performed under laboratory conditions with good control of environmental conditions. However, in this case the beam output was not controlled by a monitor chamber, as scattering conditions were more complex, and the detection of scattered radiation may have varied among different dosimeters and was affected by the beam scatter [18]. The REF is calibrated free in air and when it is used on the imaging detector's surface an additional uncertainty 0.7 % was included to consider the impact of backscattering. The CP will also produce additional scattering in the yCP condition, and when the impact of CP on K_a calibration coefficients (Eq. (3)) was studied, an additional uncertainty of 0.58 % ($k = 1$) was included in the estimated combined expanded uncertainty of 1.8 % ($k = 2$, Table 4). Because the measurements with the clinical setup were performed under laboratory conditions using reference class equipment, the uncertainties for these measurements are lower than under typical measurement conditions applied in clinical practice.

HVL measurements were based on consecutive and relative air kerma measurements, and the most systematic uncertainty components were correlated and can be ignored. The remaining components were related to statistical uncertainties and changes in spectra with and without HVL filters. The uncertainty of the air kerma ratio and the thickness of the HVL filters will impact the HVL calculation and together form the uncertainty. For the industrial setup, the estimated uncertainty for the HVL calibration coefficient was 2 % ($k = 2$), and for the clinical setup, this was 4 % ($k = 2$) because of the larger uncertainty related to HVL filter thickness. When the impact of CP was estimated (Eq. (3)), the remaining uncertainty for the ratio of calibration coefficients was 1.2 % ($k = 2$).

The X-ray tube voltage of the industrial X-ray tube was calibrated against a high voltage divider, which has a calibration uncertainty of 0.8 % ($k = 2$). The kVp values measured through the high-voltage dividers were also periodically verified by energy-calibrated spectrometry. A monitor chamber was used in the beam to control the X-ray tube output, and even small tube voltage variations could be detected and; therefore, the long-term variation was estimated to be less than 0.5 % ($u = 0.3$ %). Based on the XMM measurements, it was concluded that the different tube voltage quantities (kVp, kVp average and PPV) were within 0.1 % of each other ($u = 0.06$ %). Based on spectrometry, measurements showed that the impact of ripple was even less than that. The total uncertainty of the PPV reference values was 1.1 % ($k = 2$).

In the clinical beam, the reference PPV was estimated based on spectrometry kVp measurements. The uncertainty related to the first method is 1 % ($k = 1$, value obtained using a good statistic). In this case, the uncertainty of kVp is about 3.2 % ($k = 1$) due to the spectrum acquisition time being very short, between 4 s and 5 s. The low statistic produces fluctuations in the spectrum that reflect a large uncertainty in the parameters of the linear fit used to estimate the spectrum endpoint energy. If a beam spectrum could be acquired for a sufficiently long period of time one would also obtain an uncertainty of 1 % ($k = 1$) in the case of the mammography unit. Therefore, it was decided to use this uncertainty value associated with the first method to evaluate the endpoint energy of the spectrum, which is 1 % ($k = 1$). The uncertainty related to the second method to evaluate the endpoint energy of the spectrum is 0.1 % ($k = 1$). The uncertainty related to the rectangular distribution is 0.2 % ($k = 1$). Therefore, the total uncertainty on the mean value calculated from the two spectrum endpoint energies is, combining these uncertainties, 2 % ($k = 2$). Including the long-term stability, the uncertainty obtained for the reference tube voltage was 2.1 % ($k = 2$). The additional uncertainty components related to the XMM measurements were so small that they had only a minor impact on the combined uncertainty of the calibration coefficients. The same reference value was used for measurements in yCP and nCP; therefore, the remaining uncertainty 0.6 % ($k = 2$) for the ratio (Eq. (3)) was mainly related to the stability of the X-ray tube between the two measurements.

3. Results

3.1. Reference values

The Table 5 shows the reference values for air kerma and HVL for the industrial and clinical beams used for the measurements with and without compression paddle. The CP attenuated the air kerma by approximately 30 % and increased the HVL up to 0.05 mm Al.

The two spectrometry methods used to determine the lowest and highest reference values for kVp provided consistent results, one below and another above the nominal tube voltage value applied to the mammography system. The calculated mean value was within 0.05 kV of the nominal value, and it was decided to use the nominal tube voltage value as a reference value for PPV.

3.2. Air kerma: Calibration coefficients and impact of the CP

The calibration coefficients in terms of air kerma are given as a function of the HVL in Fig. 3. The (maximum intrinsic error) MIE was obtained for all dosimeters used, and the results of XMM1 and XMM2 were within the measurement uncertainties (3.1 %) and XMM3 just slightly exceeded that. However, XMM4, XMM5, and XMM6 exceeded the 5 % limit given in the manufacturer's specifications. The k_{kV} value was also determined to show the impact of the varying tube voltage (chapter 2.5), and only the result of XMM5 slightly exceeds the IEC limit of 5 % [11], but the limit is still within the measurement uncertainties.

Fig. 3 also shows the differences between the calibration and clinical conditions, and the results indicate the challenges related to the current calibration practice. For IC1 and IC2, the calibration or measurement conditions did not impact the calibration coefficient, and in this case, one fixed calibration coefficient can be used with an associated uncertainty of < 1 % even when MC1 with the industrial X-ray tube is used. The interpolation between different conditions can be performed using both tube voltage and HVL as radiation quality specifiers. However, in this case, it does not bring any additional benefit since there was no trend in the function of radiation quality.

As is evident from Fig. 3, the overall impact of varying conditions was larger for XMMs. It seems clear that if the XMM does not have W/Al selection, the MC1B results, i.e., the incorrect software selection of Mo/Mo for W/Al calibration, cannot be used, and the errors can be large (>10 %) if these calibration coefficients are used for incorrect conditions. Even in cases where the correct W/Al selection is available, the MC1A results do not always provide additional information on dosimeter performance regarding clinical radiation qualities. The XMM2 results were more consistent between the conditions, but with the XMM4 and XMM6, the use of the MC1A calibration coefficient would only increase the errors. The only exception was XMM5, where only the Mo/Mo selection was available and the calibration coefficient had a strong energy dependence, but it still followed the HVL. Therefore, in this case, even the MC1B results could be used to interpolate the calibration coefficients for other conditions with uncertainty of < 3.7 %, which would offer a significant improvement in accuracy.

If only the Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh conditions were considered (MC2 and MC3), the total variation of the calibration coefficient is 2–4 % for XMM1, XMM2 and XMM3, and larger than 6 % for other XMMs. This

Table 4

Combined relative (%) expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainties for calibration coefficients in different calibration and measurement conditions (MC) and their comparative ratios for nCP and yCP in terms of different quantities. A more detailed description of the different conditions is given in the text.

Condition	K_a	HVL	PPV
MC1	2.5 %	2 %	1.1 %
MC2 and MC3	3.1 %	4 %	2.1 %
nCP/yCP	1.8 %	1.2 %	0.6 %

means that even if the XMM is calibrated with one clinical radiation quality (Mo/Mo or Mo/Rh), there is still energy dependence of the related uncertainty for varying conditions. However, in the case of XMM3, XMM4, and XMM6, the use of one calibration coefficient would bring all the results closer to one, which would decrease the errors. In most cases, some trend as a function of radiation quality (HVL and tube voltage) can be observed and interpolation of the calibration coefficient based on the selected radiation quality specifier could provide a minor improvement in the selection of the most appropriate calibration coefficient. In the case of XMM5, this would significantly improve the accuracy.

If the calibration is performed in condition (2) with the correct anode/filter combination but without the CP, the only remaining impact is related to the CP. The impact of CP (Eq. (3)) when tube voltage was used to select the calibration coefficient is summarized in Table 6. With XMM5, the radiation quality specifier used for interpolation between different conditions has a major influence. If the calibration coefficient was selected based on the tube voltage, the error can be up to 8.7 %. However, when HVL was used, the difference decreased to < 2 %. The CP has consistent impact on XMM2 for Mo/Mo, introducing differences of 2–3 % depending on the radiation quality specifier used. With all the other XMMs, the impact of CP is < 2.3 % regardless of the interpolation parameter and in most cases the impact is insignificant (< estimated uncertainty of 1.8 %). However, the impact of CP was further decreased to < 1.4 % when HVL was used to select the correct calibration coefficient. The selection of incorrect CP status (MC2B) had only a minor impact on air kerma, and it was less than 0.1 % for XMM1, XMM2, XMM4, and XMM5, and it does not explain the observed differences between the measurements in nCP and yCP conditions.

3.3. HVL: Calibration coefficients and impact of the CP

The resulting calibration coefficients in terms of HVL are shown in Fig. 4. The MIE and k_{kV} were < 3.5 % for XMM1, XMM2, and XMM3, in agreement with the manufacturers' specifications. However, for XMM6, the k_{kV} and MIE were > 5 %.

In the case of HVL measurements, it is obvious that incorrect selection of radiation quality (MC1B) cannot be used. Only XMM1 allowed performing the measurement in MC1B, and the results were completely out of scale. The XMM3 did not provide any values in MC1B. The XMM2 and XMM6 have the W/Al selection, but the MC1A response was completely different from that in the clinical beams; therefore, the calibration coefficients for W/Al cannot be used for clinical measurement conditions (MC3).

If only the Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh conditions were considered (MC2 and MC3), the total variation of calibration coefficient is 4–6 % for XMM1, XMM2, and XMM3 and larger for XMM6. This was slightly decreased if only the yCP calibration coefficients were considered. This means that the use of one calibration coefficient would not significantly improve the accuracy.

The impact of CP (Eq. (3)) when tube voltage was used to select the calibration coefficient is summarized in Table 7. The XMM6 has a clear HVL dependence, and the HVL interpolation of the calibration coefficient decreases the impact of the CP from 4.8 % to 1.7 %. With the other XMMs, the impact of CP was 0.9–2.7 % regardless of the interpolation parameter, which was lower than the estimated uncertainty. The selection of incorrect CP status (MC2B) did not have a significant impact (<0.1 %) on the results.

3.4. PPV: Calibration coefficient and impact of the CP

The calibration coefficients in terms of PPV are shown in Fig. 5. For XMM1, it was not possible to measure the PPV for Mo/Rh without CP when the tube voltage was 25 kV. Only XMM2 had MIE results in agreement with the manufacturer's specifications (2 %). For the other XMMs, the MIE was between 2.5 % and 6.4 %. The IEC 61676 [24]

Table 5

The reference values for the radiation qualities used in this study for measurement conditions defined in Fig. 2 with (yCP) and without compression paddle (nCP).

Tube voltage (kV)	MC1: W/Al (nCP)		MC2: Mo/Mo (nCP)		MC3: Mo/Mo (yCP)		MC2: Mo/Rh (nCP)		MC3: Mo/Rh (yCP)	
	Air Kerma (mGy)	HVL (mm Al)	Air Kerma (mGy)	HVL (mm Al)	Air Kerma (mGy)	HVL (mm Al)	Air Kerma (mGy)	HVL (mm Al)	Air Kerma (mGy)	HVL (mm Al)
25	16.3	0.33	11.1	0.27	7.5	0.31	7.6	0.33	5.5	0.37
28	16.2	0.38	16.1	0.31	11.3	0.36	11.6	0.38	8.7	0.41
30	16.3	0.40	19.5	0.33	13.9	0.38	14.4	0.40	10.9	0.43
35	16.4	0.47	29.9	0.37	21.9	0.41	22.6	0.43	17.4	0.46

provides a MIE in absolute terms and sets the limit to 1 kV. Only XMM1 and XMM2 comply with this requirement. The XMM3 and XMM6 comply when the Mo/Mo anode/filter combination is used, but for Mo/Rh, the differences were slightly larger (1.3—1.4 kV). For XMM4, both anode/filter combinations exceed the limit, and the MIE value is 1.7 kV.

The k_{kV} was < 2.7 % for XMM1, XMM2, and XMM3, and the results can be compared with the 5 % limit given in the IEC 61676 [24] for small variation in radiation quality, defined by a change in filtration. However, for XMM4 and XMM6 k_{kV} was 5.3 % and 5.7 %, respectively, when Mo/Rh was used. This difference was 1.6 % for Mo/Mo.

In the case of PPV measurement, it is again obvious that the incorrect selection of radiation quality (MC1B) cannot be used. XMM1 and XMM3 allow the measurement of PPV in the W/Al beam with incorrect selection (Mo/Mo) for specific tube voltages (25 kV for XMM1 and XMM3 and 35 kV for XMM1), but the results were completely out of range; error of 30 % at 25 kV and 26 % at 35 kV. XMM2, XMM4, and XMM6 have W/Al selection, and the results were quite close compared to the reference value (<2.8 %). However, the results do not predict the response in clinical beams very well. Direct use of the calibration coefficient received with W/Al for clinical conditions introduces errors of 2.3 %, 9.4 % and 5.8 % for XMM2, XMM4, and XMM6, respectively, using tube voltage as the radiation specifier.

If only the Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh radiation qualities are considered (MC2 and MC3), the total variation of the calibration coefficient was around 3 % for XMM1, XMM2, and XMM4. The only exception was XMM3, where the impact of CP was much larger, and XMM6 which clearly deviated from unity at 25 kV. In most cases, the use of one calibration coefficient could bring the results closer to unity.

The PPV should be independent of CP, and the impact of the CP on the calibration coefficient (Eq. (3)) is summarized in Table 7. For XMM2, XMM4 and XMM6, the CP did not have a significant impact on the calibration coefficients and the differences were < 1 %. XMM1 had only a slightly larger CP impact < 1.8 %. The XMM3 has a significant CP impact, which increased as a function of tube voltage up to 7.1 %. In the case of PPV measurement, the selection of CP status had a major impact on PPV results, and it was 7.0 % for XMM1, 6.6 % for XMM2, and 3.6 % for XMM4. The impact of CP is shown in Table 8.

4. Discussion

The calibration coefficients for XMMs in terms of air kerma, HVL, and PPV were obtained under different measurement conditions with and without a compression paddle, and the impact of the conditions and CP on dosimeter response was studied. The results demonstrate that ionization chambers (e.g., IC1 and IC2) can be calibrated under varying conditions, but the XMMs should be calibrated using the correct radiation quality in the software selection. There will always be some differences in the conditions used for dosimeter calibrations compared to those applied in clinical measurements. The impact of these differences in measurement uncertainties should be considered in clinical practice.

For air kerma measurements, the dosimeters IC1, IC2, XMM1, XMM2, and XMM3 complied with the IEC requirements, and their performance was within the limits of 5 % for accuracy and energy

dependence of the response. The XMM5 is an older dosimeter in which only the Mo/Mo selection is available, and the manual gives clear guidance on how to correct for different radiation qualities. This detector has a larger energy dependence, but the response was almost linear as a function of HVL, allowing, in contrast to the other XMMs, interpolations between different radiation qualities. XMM4 and XMM6 had slightly larger variations from reference values, but their energy dependence was still within the acceptable limits, and therefore both would comply with the accuracy requirement of 5 % with proper calibration.

The end users should consider their target accuracy. The IAEA TRS-457 recommends 7 % uncertainty ($k = 2$) for the measurable quantities [22], which is difficult to achieve if the a priori declared errors are close to 5 %. To achieve traceability and improve accuracy, calibration is required. The air kerma calibration coefficients for the ionization chambers can be interpolated with good accuracy from values received using different radiation qualities and conditions (nCP and yCP). This is not the case with most XMMs. In this study, the calibration coefficients for different radiation qualities varied significantly, but the response did not follow a clear function, except for XMM5, indicating that interpolations between different radiation qualities would often be impossible.

It was evident that the XMMs can only be used with the correct radiation quality selection, and incorrect selection can introduce errors as large as 10 %, as shown in this study. Therefore, if the XMM does not offer a correct selection for the clinical beam to be measured, it is essential to know how changes in the conditions will influence the response of the dosimeter. This is a very relevant consideration in the measurements of new mammography devices and corresponding new X-ray spectra. In addition, this applies to the situation where a nominally correct radiation quality is adjusted by additional attenuators such as aluminium sheets in HVL measurements. XMMs should not be used for HVL measurements with aluminium sheets because the spectra will change every time when an additional filter is added in the beam.

The impact of CP on air kerma response was up to 2–3 %, implying that it should be accounted for if more accurate measurements are required, but its effect was relatively small in relation to the effects induced by differences between radiation qualities. When the software selection in the XMM was correct, i.e., the same as the clinical anode/filter combination in the mammography equipment, the impact of the compression paddle on the response of the dosimeter was, in most cases, reasonably low (<2%). Clinical mammography measurements are performed with different types of compression paddles, and their impact on radiation quality should be considered in accurate measurements, and in estimated uncertainties. XMM calibrations are typically performed without a compression paddle in the beam, and therefore, the laboratory could consider providing additional data on how the response of that XMM changes when radiation quality is slightly altered. If this data is not available, an additional uncertainty of 2 % ($k = 1$) could be used as a typical estimate, at least for air kerma measurements.

The data showed that dosimeters XMM1, XMM2 and XMM3 were suitable for HVL measurements, and the results comply with manufacturers' specifications for accuracy within 5 %. The energy dependence of

Fig. 3. Calibration coefficient in terms of air kerma (N_{ka}) for different anode/filter combinations without compression paddle (nCP) and with compression paddle (yCP). For the results of W/Al anode/filter, and the black colour indicates that correct W/Al selection was available in the detector, and the # symbol and purple colour indicate that the incorrect had to be used and Mo/Mo was selected instead. The estimated uncertainty ($k = 2$) is 2.5 % for W/Al and 3.1 % for Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh. The lines are used to show the connection between the measurement points, and they do not have physical reasoning.

the response was somewhat high. Incorrect selection of radiation quality can introduce large errors for HVL measurements (up to 14 %), but the correct selection of CP status appears not to be so crucial, at least for the measurement of HVL. Similar to the results for air kerma, the impact of CP on the response for HVL calibrations is up to 2–3 %, i.e., it should be

considered when higher accuracy is required.

For the clinical X-ray tube, a high voltage divider was not available, and we had to find another way to define the reference values for PPV. Although they can provide the most accurate results for the tube voltage and allow measurement of the voltage ripple and pulse shape, high

Table 6

Impact (Eq. (3) of the use/non-use of compression paddle (%) on the calibration coefficients for air kerma measurements of different dosimeters when tube voltage is used as a radiation quality specifier. Values shown in italic style exceed the estimated measurement uncertainty (1.8%, Table 4).

Tube Voltage (kV)	Mo/Mo							
	IC1	IC2	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM4	XMM5	XMM6
25	0.8	1.1	1.3	1.4	0.8	1.1	8.7	2.3
28	0.5	0.5	0.4	1.8	0.5	0.4	7.2	2.2
30	0.7	0.7	0.4	1.4	0.7	0.2	6.6	2.0
35	0.7	0.8	0.3	1.3	0.7	0.4	5.7	0.8

Tube Voltage (kV)	Mo/Rh							
	IC1	IC2	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM4	XMM5	XMM6
25	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.9	4.6	0.6
28	0.6	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.5	1.7	4.1	0.9
30	0.4	0.1	0.3	1.0	0.6	1.2	3.5	1.0
35	0.4	0.4	0.1	0.6	0.4	0.9	3.2	0.8

Fig. 4. Calibration coefficient in terms of half-value layer (N_{HVL}) for different anode/filter combinations without compression paddle (nCP) and with compression paddle (yCP). For the results of W/Al anode/filter, the black colour indicates correct W/Al selection. For XMM1 the # symbol and purple colour indicate that the incorrect selection had to be used and Mo/Mo was selected instead. In this case 3/4 results are out of scale and not shown here. The estimated uncertainty ($k = 2$) is 2 % for W/Al and 4 % for Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh. The lines are used to show the connection between the measurement points, and they do not have physical reasoning.

Table 7

Impact (Eq. (3) of the compression paddle (%) on the calibration coefficients for half-value layer measurements using different dosimeters when tube voltage is used as a radiation quality specifier. Values shown in italic style exceed the estimated measurement uncertainty (1.2%, Table 4).

Tube Voltage (kV)	Mo				Rh			
	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM6	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM6
25	2.6	1.4	2.5	4.3	1.5	0.8	1.1	3.0
28	0.1	1.5	0.4	4.0	0.4	0.2	0.2	2.8
30	0.1	1.0	0.2	4.8	0.8	1.7	0.4	3.5
35	0.1	0.3	0.9	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.7	2.4

voltage dividers are not typically available for clinical mammography devices and presence of a protective resistor may cause a deviation between the voltage divider result and actual tube potential [21]. Therefore, the reference PPV was estimated based on spectrometry. Fig. 5 shows that for the clinical X-ray tube, the PPV results of the XMM

measurements did not fully comply with the manufacturers' specifications for accuracy. Incorrect radiation quality selection can introduce large errors (here up to 30 %), and the correct selection of CP existence seems to be crucial for PPV measurements. The impact of CP on the response was significant for XMM3 but small for others. Therefore, the

Fig. 5. Calibration coefficients in terms of practical peak voltage (N_{PPV}) for different anode/filter combinations without compression paddle (nCP) and with compression paddle (yCP). For the results of W/Al anode/filter, the black colour was used to indicate that the correct W/Al selection was available. The estimated uncertainty ($k = 2$) is 1.1 % for W/Al and 2.1 % for Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh. The lines are used to show the connection between the measurement points, and they do not have physical reasoning.

Table 8

Impact (Eq. (3) of the compression paddle (%) on the practical peak voltage for the Mo and Rh filters for different dosimeters. Values shown in italic style exceed the estimated measurement uncertainty (0.6%, Table 4).

Tube Voltage (kV)	Mo					Rh				
	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM4	XMM6	XMM1	XMM2	XMM3	XMM4	XMM6
25	1.1	0.8	2.8	0.7	0.6	*	N.A	0.8	1.0	0.7
28	1.3	0.7	4.7	0.6	0.7	1.4	N.A	1.8	0.9	0.1
30	1.6	0.7	5.3	0.7	0.2	0.7	N.A	3.8	0.5	0.2
35	1.8	0.9	7.1	0.9	0.2	1.4	1.0	5.6	0.1	0.2

*Did not measure.

results showed that in most cases, calibration can be performed without CP. However, during the commissioning of new dosimeters, it would be recommendable to study how small changes in radiation quality affect the response of the dosimeter and to consider these in uncertainty estimations.

The end user should evaluate the accepted level of uncertainty for their measurements. When the measured values are used for acceptance

of X-ray systems, more strict limits might be required [28]. If the values are used for quality control and repeated measurements, the absolute uncertainty might not be so relevant, and the stability of the response is more important. In digital mammography, the accuracy of tube voltage is sometimes not considered essential for image quality [29,30]. However, the stability of the tube voltage might still be relevant for the mammography system performance and the PPV measurement gives

more specific data on the X-ray tube performance than an averaging HVL value. In mammography the accuracy of HVL might be essential when it is used to estimate the mean granular dose (MGD).

The limitation of the study was that only one clinical mammography system, one compression paddle, a limited number of radiation qualities, and dosimeters were available for the investigation. Further research would thus be justified. The clinical radiation qualities were limited to Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh anode/filter combinations because they were available in the laboratory. Mo/Mo is still defined in the IEC 61267 [10] standard as the reference and is commonly used for calibration. However, in clinical practice, a large variety of different radiation qualities are used, and W-anode –based radiation qualities have become more common in modern devices [31,32]. The impact of the energy dependence of the XMM's response should be studied on a larger scale of radiation qualities to obtain a full understanding of the related uncertainties. However, the data from this study can be used to indicate the order of magnitude of the uncertainties. In most cases, only one unit of each type of XMM was used, and the inter-variability among the same type of XMM should be studied. The focus of this study was on the changes in calibration conditions, radiation quality, and compression paddle usage. However, the study can be further improved by studying the impact of varying scatter conditions.

In general, the calibration conditions should be selected so that they represent the clinical measurement conditions. However, the variety of these conditions is extensive and increasing, and it is not possible to cover all the conditions in practical calibrations. It is common practice that dosimeters used in mammography are calibrated without a compression paddle, whereas in clinics, the compression paddle should be in the beam when measurements are performed, and the result aims to estimate the radiation dose to the patient. The discrepancy in the procedures introduces an additional uncertainty component that should be observed when accurate measurements are required. A major challenge in including CP in calibration practice is that the specifications of clinically used CPs are not standardized. Furthermore, the impact of the differences in conditions between the calibration process and clinical measurements should be included in the uncertainty budget. In this respect, this study has provided indications of the range of uncertainties encountered with different XMMs and irradiation conditions.

5. Conclusions

The dosimetry equipment must be calibrated to provide traceability for clinical measurements. The calibration coefficient is provided for specific conditions and radiation quality. Because the clinical measurements are performed in varying situations, the difference between calibration and clinical conditions should be considered in the uncertainty budget. In this study, detector responses under different measurement conditions were compared and related uncertainties were estimated. Calibration coefficients of ionization chambers can be interpolated with less than 2 % uncertainty due to their low sensitivity to changes in conditions. However, the response of XMMs varies in such a way under various conditions that the calibration coefficient applicable to the practical mammography radiation quality and condition cannot be predicted. XMMs should be used for clinical measurements in mammography only when correct settings are available. When not available, XMMs should not be used or used only with caution (e.g., with comprehensive testing). Uncertainties related to small changes in radiation quality, e.g., by introducing a compression paddle, can still be acceptable, but the resulting total uncertainty should also be considered. The requirement for calibration coverage is directly dependent on the parameter accuracy required in clinical measurements. If the aim is to perform measurements with 7 % ($k = 2$) uncertainty recommended by the IAEA [22], calibration should be performed in conditions that are close to those in use in clinical practice.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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